

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Impact of SO ₂ on the thermodynamic properties of CO ₂ -rich fluids
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	CCSProp
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	SINTEF ECCSEL Energy Fluid Lab
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	CCUS, phase equilibrium, binary mixtures, CO ₂ -SO ₂ , thermodynamic properties
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	21.04.2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	04.05.2024 → 14 days at location of RI
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	22.04.2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	03.05.2024 → 12 days of access
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	3
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	The RI was not used during the weekend and due to the public holiday on the 1st of May.
Number of days using the RI	9
Number of users granted access (group size)	2
Comments	Only one user (User group member 2) of the group participated in the exchange.
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>Carbon-based chemicals can be produced with CO₂ and hydrogen in Power-to-X processes. In this way, renewable energy can be stored to compensate its fluctuations, while overcoming the challenges of hydrogen storage and application due to the low energy density of hydrogen. CO₂ can be captured from the flue gas of industrial processes and must be transported and (intermediately) stored. When capturing CO₂, CO₂ is infused with some impurities which influence the properties of CO₂. SO₂ is one of the main impurities and has some disadvantages such as the corrosive effect but also some advantages, for example the increase of density at specific SO₂ contents, which theoretically allows to store more CO₂ in a certain reservoir.</p>	

Since pressure and temperature change while transporting and storing CO₂, it is crucial to understand the influence of the impurities on the properties of CO₂. Therefore, the aim of the proposed exchange was to gain knowledge on how SO₂ impacts the thermodynamic properties of CO₂-rich fluids. Hence, phase equilibrium measurements of different CO₂-SO₂ mixtures with 6 pressures at constant temperatures should be investigated. This results in an equilibrium curve and should improve the data situation of such systems.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The CO₂-Mix – VLE lab at the SINTEF ECCSEL Energy Fluid Lab allows to perform highly accurate phase equilibrium measurements of CO₂-rich mixtures.

First, the CO₂-mix – VLE lab must be calibrated, whereby it is important to ensure that calibrations are performed within a wide range of all possible mixtures. Therefore, different compositions with which the calibration is carried out, are defined as follows:

1. 90 vol.-% of CO₂, 10 vol.-% of SO₂
2. 10 vol.-% of SO₂, 90 vol.-% of CO₂
3. 70 vol.-% of CO₂, 30 vol.-% of SO₂
4. 30 vol.-% of SO₂, 70 vol.-% of CO₂
5. 50 vol.-% of SO₂, 50 vol.-% of CO₂

These CO₂-SO₂ mixtures were produced in a separate facility, RefGasMix, for accurate gravimetric preparation of CO₂-rich mixtures and are considered as calibration gas mixtures.

Hence, the calibration was performed with these compositions. Before every calibration point, the system is emptied and evacuated. The system is then flushed with the new gas mixture at least three times to ensure that there are no traces of other gas mixtures in the system.

The calibration of the first composition was performed and the system was emptied, evacuated and flushed twice with the fourth composition. Unfortunately, a leak was detected during the second flushing process. The leak was found to be in the pump of the system, where an O-ring was damaged. Unfortunately, the system could not be repaired within my stay, which is why no experiments were performed with this system and the proposed work could not be carried out. Instead, I was able to get some insights of other experimental set ups in the SINTEF ECCSEL Energy Fluid Lab. Among them were the DeFACTO set up, a set up with different flow and density meters, and some more. I will go into more detail for the first two setups:

DeFACTO is a vertical flow installation enabling the circulation of fluids through a 90 m deep loop. The facility is equipped with over 100 high precision-fast response pressure and temperature sensors, thus allowing to study injection and flow of chemical energy carrier fluids or underground thermal or mechanical storage. During my stay, experiments with a CO₂-N₂ mixture were performed. The aim is to collect experimental data to verify simulations of the tube and the injection point. An experiment with a CO₂-N₂ mixture with 2 vol.-% of N₂ was performed. The CO₂-N₂ mixture was prepared, and the temperature and pressure were adjusted. When equilibrium was reached, the CO₂-N₂ mixture was pumped down to the loop, which simulates the well. Thereby, data of pressures and temperatures was collected. During injection temperature and therefore the pressure fluctuated. To stabilize and control the parameters an additional heat circuit is implemented in the facility.

Experiments with a setup, where flow meters and density meters are tested, were conducted aiming at creating reference measurement methods. The set up consists of four flow meters, two density meters and a pump. The flow meters are ultrasonic sound meters, whereby four of them are installed on different locations. An ultrasonic flow meter consists of a transmitter and a receiver, arranged oppositely. A signal is sent from the transmitter to the receiver and the velocity of the flow can be calculated based on the defined distance and the time it takes for the signal to

travel from the transmitter to the receiver. One of the density meters is a Coriolis density meter, the other is a rheologic sensor. During my stay, the setup was filled with CO₂ and static and dynamic experiments were performed at different temperature and pressure levels of CO₂.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Unfortunately, the planned experiments with the CO₂-SO₂ mixture could not be conducted due to the leakage in the CO₂-Mix – VLE lab. However, the calibration of the first calibration gas was successful and the desired accuracy was yield.

Since I was accompanying team members when conducting other experiments, I can only present results, which were directly analyzed during experiments. The exact data was not provided due to confidentiality reasons.

The experiment in the DeFacto facility reached stable conditions for a few 100 s in the end. The stable conditions in the well are at 66 bar and 23-24°C, whereby small fluctuations of around 0,5 bar and 0,5°C occur. In the end of the experiments, when stable conditions were reached, CO₂ ran out, which is why the experiment was not continued and the stable conditions could only be held for a few 100s. Subsequently, the data of the experiments will be compared to simulations allowing the simulations to be validated.

Sufficient results were yield in the experiments with flow and density meters. Several measurements of the flow and the density were undertaken at temperatures from -5 °C up to 26,2 °C and the corresponding pressure. The measured density with both sensors differs from the theoretical density with around 5 kg/m³. The measured flow velocity on all four sensors achieved sufficient accuracy of around 0,1-0,3 % compared to theoretical values.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

For the interpretation of the results, the exact data should be considered. However, it can be concluded that the experiments in the DeFacto lab yield sufficient data, which is used to compare with simulations. The tests of the flow meters have been successful as an accuracy within the given tolerance specification was achieved. The tests of the density meter conclude that the measured values of both sensors are similar but deviate slightly from the theoretical density. One reason could be, that temperatures within the setup vary slightly from the temperature with which the theoretical density is calculated. Therefore, the setup must be checked, whether the assumed temperature for the theoretical calculation is correct. Also, it is planned to test another density meter, which is then compared to the two sensors which are already installed. In this way, a better understanding of these deviations should be gained.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

Since the planned experiments could not be conducted, I was able to accompany the members of the team when other types of experiments in the Energy Fluid Lab were performed. Therefore, I was able to gain first-hand experience in the lab and got to know different types of research infrastructure. Taking part in different experiments allowed me to gain a deeper understanding of lab work. Also, I could broaden my knowledge in the field of CCS and Energy topics, which gives me a better understanding of research needs in this field. Overall, the transnational access was characterized by an enriching exchange of knowledge.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)					
Unfortunately, there was a failure of the CO ₂ -Mix – VLE lab early into the test campaign, which is why the proposed work could not be completed. A leakage in the pump of the facility occurred due to the corrosive properties of the used chemicals. Even though, the team at SINTEF worked hard to repair the setup, it could not be fixed in time.					
Intended publications					
None					
Data management					
User report and summary of information (lessons learned, work performed) will be stored on the server of AIT.					
Conclusions / additional comments					
Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The application process was good. I have one small comment/suggestion: After the application, I didn't receive any confirmation e-mail, whether the application worked or not.					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I was told that the document with the general rules was out of date. So, I had to ask when I needed information, but I always got a very helpful and quick response.					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems.				
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				

RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The planned experiments involved CO₂ and SO₂ (toxic). CO₂ is a non-toxic and non-combustible gas but is one of the main greenhouse gases responsible for the greenhouse effect and global warming. SO₂ is toxic by inhalation and may irritate eyes and mucous membranes. https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Carbon-Dioxide https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Sulfur-Dioxide</p> <p>However, due to the failure in the setup, the experimental campaign was changed. Therefore, I only worked with CO₂, but no SO₂.</p>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The planned experiments involved CO₂ and SO₂ (toxic). CO₂ is a non-toxic and non-combustible gas but is one of the main greenhouse gases responsible for the greenhouse effect and global warming. SO₂ is toxic by inhalation and may irritate eyes and mucous membranes. https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Carbon-Dioxide https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Sulfur-Dioxide</p> <p>However, due to the failure in the setup, the experimental campaign was changed. Therefore, I only worked with CO₂, but no SO₂.</p>	
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details.

	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>							
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
None											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
None											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											
Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										

Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.